

Imagination, Myth, and Applicability: Value Formation in Post-Secular Education

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Abstract

In post-secular and pluralist educational contexts, value formation risks either normative imposition or pedagogical withdrawal. This paper argues that imagination and myth provide a non-coercive framework for ethical and existential formation. Through a conceptual–hermeneutical engagement with J.R.R. Tolkien’s distinction between allegory and applicability, it shows how mythic narratives disclose meaning symbolically while preserving interpretive freedom. Applicability is proposed as a pedagogical orientation that enables openness to transcendence without presupposing shared metaphysical commitments, thereby reconfiguring the educator’s role as steward of interpretive space rather than as a transmitter of values.

Keywords

imagination; myth; value formation; applicability; post-secular education; philosophy of education; transcendence; Tolkien.

Introduction

In the contemporary educational field, the issue of how values are transmitted is particularly thorny. Post-secular and pluralist contexts undermine the existence of shared symbolic, moral, or religious – in brief, metaphysical – frameworks. Yet, the educator is often caught between the felt obligation to offer moral and spiritual orientation and the imperative to respect the diversity of convictions (or lack thereof) among their students. This is primarily a pedagogical issue before becoming a political one. When values are claimed vertically, they risk being felt imposed, and naturally rejected as irrelevant or coercive; on the other hand, when one keeps back from at least trying to pass on values in the name of political correctness, the educational process deteriorates into mere procedural competence.

The situation is further intensified by the growing influence of technological and artificial intelligence tools in the educational setting, which promise greater appeal. While such instruments offer increased protagonism and access to information for students, they provide less human formation. Education becomes increasingly conceived in terms of optimisation and efficiency. Undoubtedly, familiarity with these tools is invaluable in today’s society, yet they remain largely silent on how students perceive meaning, learn to inhabit values, and develop

moral and spiritual orientations. There is no way such dimensions can be touched satisfactorily by an algorithmic process. Thus, the question: how can education nurture ethical and existential formation without being either imposingly didactic or normatively withdrawing?

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate how mythology and imagination can constitute indispensable pedagogical resources in addressing this dilemma. “Imagination,” here, is understood as the pre-conceptual capacity to perceive and inhabit meaning beyond what is immediately given. This capacity is present already at an early age. Imagination thus mediates between experience and understanding, enabling students to encounter values as possibilities rather than receive them passively as predetermined norms. Mythic narratives, in turn, function as symbolic spaces in which meaning can be encountered, explored, and possibly wilfully appropriated. Yet even here, the educational potential of narrative should not be taken for granted. Stories, too, can be reduced to bearers of predetermined lessons, thereby diminishing their power. This could happen either because of the educator’s own “political” orientation or because of curricular constraints. J.R.R. Tolkien’s reflections on myth and fairy-stories¹ are useful for sensitising the educator to the risks involved when narratives are employed too allegorically. Tolkien will help us see how imagination shapes moral perception prior to conceptual moral judgement, and how openness to transcendence can be nurtured without relying on shared metaphysical commitments.

Literature Positioning and Methodological Orientation

Recent research in education has given considerable attention to both value transmission in pluralist contexts and the role of imagination in primary and secondary schools. Studies related to values tend to focus on school climate, teacher values and institutional norms (e.g. Auer et al. 2023; Kunter et al. 2024), while the studies on imagination often frame it in terms of creativity, engagement, or cognitive development (e.g., Aydın 2023; Elmira et al. 2022) rather than as a tool for meaning-making. Still, these two bodies of research hardly enter into sustained dialogue. More specifically, little consideration has been given to the mythic narrative forms through which imagination mediates encounters with values and meaning. Likewise, little attention has been given to the pedagogical risks of reducing stories to carriers of pre-fixed messages. Considering the near-universality of myth across cultures, myth could be a promising educational resource in post-secular and multicultural settings, as it discloses meaning symbolically and pre-conceptually, that is, without presupposing a shared metaphysical context.

This paper will, therefore, address this conceptual gap. It will proceed through a conceptual-hermeneutical approach that engages in a dialogical reading across literary theory and philosophy of education. I will not be advancing an empirical or normative model of practice, but rather, seek to clarify conceptual distinctions that illuminate how meaning and values are

¹Tolkien’s understanding of these two categories of stories overlaps, but it is beyond the scope of this paper to delve into how he distinguishes them and how he keeps them together. In this paper, *myth* and *fairy-stories* will be used interchangeably. The hyphenation of “fairy-stories” is according to Tolkien’s use.

constructed in educational contexts. A close reading of Tolkien's writings on myth, allegory and applicability will offer a theoretical resource for disclosing pedagogical dynamics that often remain merely implicit in contemporary educational discourse. By placing Tolkien's literary thoughts about imaginative meaning-making in dialogue with current issues in the philosophy of education, this paper aims to offer a pedagogical orientation that promotes student agency and openness to transcendence within a pluralist societal and cultural context.

Narratives, Myth and the Problem of Value Imposition

Charles Taylor's notion of cross pressures within the contemporary immanent frame helps illuminate the pedagogical dilemma of value transmission. Taylor's philosophy can help us understand how we at once *feel* the need to transmit values, and, at the same time, are concerned not to overstep. "The whole culture experiences cross pressures, between the draw of the narratives of closed immanence on one side, and the sense of their inadequacy on the other, strengthened by encounter with [...] some intimations of the transcendent." (Taylor 2018, 595) In this light, both sides of the value-transmission dilemma mentioned above betray the educational process if this process is meant to accompany the growth of a holistically healthy and socially emancipated person.

As indicated in the introduction, narratives, too, can be risky. Stories can be deeply representational, even allegorical, or totally anti-representational, to the extent that they are linked to life only with difficulty and by individuals dedicated to literature or philosophy. Furthermore, the difficulty being explored does not pertain solely to literary education. Thus, the mere presence of narrative does not guarantee adequate formation.

This is why myth is presented in this paper as a particular type of narrative that mitigates the risks just mentioned. It is important to clarify immediately that, by "myth," I do not mean simply a story of ancient origin that concerns gods and other supernatural beings. These stories have often been divested of their mythic quality when told in a way that strips them of their transformative power. When this happens, these stories become mere entertainment with minimal educational value. Compare, for example, Walt Disney's versions of Snow White and Hercules with the earliest recorded versions of the same characters and stories. Such narratives became treated as empty containers for subjective projection, and the educational process was reduced to the facilitation of preferences rather than an encounter with meaning. Conversely, old stories have sometimes been instrumentalised long after their creation: pre-fixed meanings are imposed, and imaginative engagement is subordinated to interpretive control. Think, for example, of the misuse of Norse mythology by Hitler's regime. Here, the control of meaning rendered the narratives instruments of symbolic dominance rather than sites of shared exploration. Rather, the mythic quality of myth lies in its form of imaginative expression, where meaning is symbolically disclosed and encountered rather than discursively explained, so that the listener or reader is motivated, inspired, or invited to change or grow without losing their free agency.

A myth, then, could be a story written in modernity, or even in our contemporary time. The educator is thus not externally restricted in their choice of stories. Neither are they divested of

the responsibility to choose the stories. Yet they have the added professional and ethical responsibility to allow the chosen stories to be read freely, without manipulating their meaning to conform to presumed external norms or draining them of meaning entirely.

It is at this point that Tolkien's distinction between allegory and applicability becomes useful. Unlike much work on narrative education that presupposes the positive formative efficacy of stories, this paper aims to identify the conditions under which mythic narrative sustains value formation, and proposes applicability as a conceptual criterion to help distinguish between pedagogical openness and masked imposition.

Tolkien's Pedagogical Contribution: Myth as Art and Applicability

Central to Tolkien's consideration of myths is their treatment primarily as works of art. This is an essential approach if meaning is not to be imposed or drained, but to be discovered. For Tolkien, myth is a (sub-)creation of humanity, the finest of the arts for its heightened engagement with imagination, which eludes thorough analysis because, like all art, it has value in itself beyond any possible external references (Tolkien 2014). Like all art, myth can indeed be analysed, but never to the point of exhausting meaning. In reference to his own *The Lord of the Rings*, which he considered to have a mythic quality, he wrote that it has a life of its own: "Of course *The L.R.* does not belong to me. It has been brought forth and must now go its appointed way in the world, though naturally I take a deep interest in its fortunes, as a parent would of a child" (Tolkien 2023, 579). Tolkien's reflections on myth throughout his life extend beyond history, folklore, comparative mythology, philology, and even aesthetics. For Tolkien, myth sustains a symbolic world that bears meaning without being reduced to clear-cut external references. Tolkien maintains that this is the fullest artistic realisation of the imagination.

In this reflective context, we encounter his critique of allegory, or simplistic representational narratives. "I am not naturally attracted (in fact much the reverse) by allegory, mystical or moral" (Tolkien 2023, 492). Allegory, as Tolkien understands it, establishes a simple one-to-one correspondence between elements in the narrative and external meanings. This closes the interpretive space between the reader and the story. For Tolkien, this undermines the narrative's artistic integrity, and meaning cannot be encountered but only decoded. Recognition, rather than participation, becomes the reader's part. However, Tolkien does not stop at this critique. "That there is no allegory does not, of course, say there is no applicability. There always is" (Tolkien 2023, 377). Unlike allegory, applicability does not deny the presence of *inherent* meaning, and neither does it collapse interpretation into either subjectivism or absolutism. Applicability preserves a space in which meaning can be encountered and picked up according to the reader's situation, experience, and moral horizon. "I think many confuse 'applicability' with 'allegory'; but the one resides in the freedom of the reader, and the other in the purposed domination of the author" (Tolkien 2021, xix). Applicability recognises that stories may mean different things to different readers without ending in arbitrariness. Through applicability, the significance of a story unfolds through engagement. For Tolkien, this openness is the defining strength of myth as art.

Another characteristic stance adopted by Tolkien is on the assumed suitability of fairy-stories for children. This clarification is essential to avoid misunderstanding the full scope of this paper. I am not arguing that myth is particularly suited in education because it is particularly suitable for children. My argument is that myth is particularly suited because it grants the imagination freedom without dissolving into ethical irrelevance. Tolkien was strong in his opinion that good fairy-stories, or myths, are not primarily written for children. “If fairy-story as a kind is worth reading at all it is worthy to be written for and read by adults. [...] Then, as a branch of genuine art, children may hope to get fairy-stories fit for them to read and yet within their measure” (Tolkien 2014, 58). Rather than relegating fairy-stories to the nursery, Tolkien believed that they are ideal to promote growth, precisely because they are not primarily childish.

But it is one of the lessons of fairy-stories (if we can speak of the lessons of things that do not lecture) that on callow, lumpish, and selfish youth peril, sorrow, and the shadow of death can bestow dignity, and even sometimes wisdom. [...] Their books like their clothes should allow for growth, and their books at any rate should encourage it. (Tolkien 2014, 58)

Children, according to Tolkien, do not need stories to be simplified, diluted, or moralised as has happened with many fairy-stories in popular culture. Children and youth, according to Tolkien require space to inhabit stories. Tolkien’s perspective challenges educational approaches that underestimate the interpretative agency of students and so seek to control meaning, possibly out of fear of misunderstanding.

Implications for the Education to Transcendence

From an educational standpoint, therefore, applicability can be understood as a guiding orientation rather than a method. Tolkien’s pedagogical contribution does not prescribe particular techniques but points to a criterion by which educational practices may be evaluated. In practice, whether in formal or non-formal educational moments, applicability may appear when students discuss a narrative’s moments of loss or moral ambiguity without being guided toward a predetermined lesson, allowing connections to emerge from their own experiences. Similarly, in pluralist religious education, biblical parables read alongside myths from other traditions invite reflection on justice, forgiveness, or hope without collapsing into doctrinal conclusions, so that transcendence is encountered rather than asserted. Even in early formation, fairy-stories read without moral summarisation return in children’s play and conversation, where values are imaginatively inhabited rather than verbally imposed.

Applicability empowers education to transcendence without enforcing belief, and to sustain normativity without coercion. It opens a formative space where imagination mediates between tradition and appropriation. Rather than a doctrinal claim, transcendence is introduced as a dimension of meaning that exceeds instrumentalising rationality. This orientation brings a paradigmatic shift from efficiency of transmission to the very possibility of formation. In this framework, imagination becomes the medium through which values become perceptible as lived possibilities. Rather than superior *content*, myths convey a symbolic density that sustains applicability respectfully across diverse horizons.

The technological and digital influences in contemporary education do not cancel the value of this insight. Algorithmic systems cannot substitute the value of imaginative processing of meaning and values. While algorithmic logic is based on optimisation, prediction, and efficiency, mythic meaning-making is built upon symbolic excess, non-exhaustibility, and applicability. Like rationality and imagination, technology and AI, and mythic meaning-making, complement one another across different dimensions of the human person. Thus, imagination and applicability reframe the educator's role. Rather than simply a transmitter of values, the educator becomes a steward of interpretive space. Far from abdication from responsibility, educational authority is lived through the selection of stories, framing, and accompaniment, rather than through control.

Conclusion

This paper has argued that imagination and myth are indispensable resources for educational formation in post-secular and pluralist contexts. It has shown these as means of reconfiguring how meaning and values are passed. It diagnosed allegorical pedagogy as high risk for value imposition, which inhibits imaginative engagement and potentially leads to undesirable outcomes such as ineffectiveness or fundamentalism. In response, it retrieved Tolkien's distinction between allegory and applicability and proposed the latter as a pedagogical orientation that avoids both value imposition and withdrawal, making value and meaning available for discovery or encounter.

Applicability allows the imagination to mediate between authority and freedom in the formation of morals and values. Through applicability, the students can inhabit meaning rather than being forced to assent to it. This preserves both the mythic narrative and the student's agency.

While I intentionally retained a non-confessional stance, in conclusion to this paper, I would like to open a suggestive horizon for those educational traditions that have long valued the graduality of meaning formation over the transmission of propositions. Branches of Catholic educational thought, for example, which emphasise symbol, narrative, and the cultivation of a moral imagination, could find in applicability a conceptual perspective from which pedagogical intuitions can be reinterpreted and reinstated in contemporary pluralist contexts. Within such Catholic thought, applicability would be useful in sustaining a healthy moral imagination non-coercively and thus be more fully universal. Further exploration of this goes beyond the present scope, but it could offer a fruitful area for dialogue between philosophy of education, theology and practice.

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